

BIOCHEMICAL NUTRITION FAMILY PLANT RUTE-LEMON LEAVED

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Annotation: The article studied rue leaves fed from leaves - a family of dicotyledonous dioecious plants of the order Sapindoflora. Representatives of the genus Citrus, the lemon, are of the greatest importance to humans.

Key words: Photosynthesis, glycerophosphate, 3-phosphoglyceric acid, glucose-6-phosphate, fructose-6-phosphate, glucose, fructose, sucrose.

INTRODUCTION

Plants growing on land annually absorb about 20 billion tons of carbon in the form of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, or an average of 1300 kg per 1 ha, the totality of plants, including seaweed, about 150 billion tons. Terrestrial plants process 4217 kJ of cosmic solar energy into assimilation products annually.

Photosynthetic activity depends on the species characteristics of the plant, the age of individual leaves and the entire plant, the intensity and wavelength of light, and the level of nitrogen nutrition.

Only 2-4% of the solar energy falling on the surface of vegetative plants is used for the synthesis of organic substances. The rest is spent on transpiration and reflection. The plant evaporates water for cooling. The evaporation process itself is associated with a large expenditure of energy. More than 25% of solar energy is spent on evaporation by leaves, in the southern regions - up to 70-95%, which is about 10-45 times more than is stored in the crop.

One of the tasks of modern science is to find ways to increase the utilization of solar energy.

For the formation of complex organic substances from the primary products of photosynthesis, the energy generated in the plant as a result of respiratory processes is expended, that is, the oxidation of carbohydrates with oxygen. This process is the opposite of photosynthesis:

The energy released during respiration is used to:

1. synthesis of other organic compounds;

2. absorption of salts and water from the soil by roots and their movement through parts of the plant;

3. making roots work in the soil during their growth.

The energy of respiration is also used to overcome the resistance of the soil during germination by the sprouts.

The energy released in the process of respiratory oxidation of substances passes into a specific form of energy storage - macroergic phosphate bonds of adenosine triphosphoric acid (ATP).

Macroergic compounds can be divided into two groups:

1. glycerophosphate, 3-phosphoglyceric acid, glucose-6-phosphate, fructose-6-phosphate. Compounds of this group accumulate from 0.8 to 3.0 kkal per 1 mol of substance;

2. adenosine triphosphoric acid (ATP), adenosine diphosphoric acid (ADP), 1,3-diphosphoglyceric acid, phosphoenolpyruvic acid. Compounds of this group accumulate from 6 to 16 kcal per 1 mol.

In all metabolic reactions, energy is used in conjugated processes of release and use of energy, and the transfer of energy from one reaction to another can only be when two reactions proceed sequentially and have common intermediate products. So, the formation of sucrose can proceed in conjunction with the hydrolysis of ATP:

Total:

Similarly, the processes of formation of starch from glucose, proteins from amino acids proceed.

In dry, hot years with dry winds, photosynthesis in plants is possible only in the early morning and evening hours. The rest of the time there is a loss of plastic substances and energy for resistance and protective reactions to adverse environmental conditions (moisture deficiency and elevated temperature). In this case, the balance between the formation and consumption of high-energy phosphorus compounds is disturbed, the energy potential decreases, the oxidative potential in the cell increases, which leads to the oxidative destruction of carbohydrates and proteins, in connection with which ammonia accumulates in the tissues of the plant organism and their poisoning occurs.

A positive effect of phosphorus and potassium on the water content of protoplasm colloids was noted, which leads to a decrease in moisture

consumption for transpiration. Plant tissues provided with phosphorus are characterized by high water-holding capacity. Such plants have a more stable water exchange, due to an increase in the content of osmotically and colloidally bound water, increased hydration of protoplasm components. Especially the effect of phosphorus is manifested in conditions of insufficient water supply in the early periods of plant development [1-8].

EXPERIMENTAL PART

The absorption of nutrients is not always a consequence of their need for the plant. This is the main disadvantage of chemical diagnostic methods. In addition, a lack or excess of elements can lead to a disruption in the absorption of other nutrients by plants. Thus, a deficiency of phosphorus leads to the accumulation of nitrates, and boron - to a deficiency. However, this has nothing to do with nitrogen nutrition.

Functional diagnostic methods make it possible to assess the need of plants for nutrients by determining the intensity of physiological and biochemical processes. Thus, the level of supply and need for nitrogen is determined by the ability of tissues to restore nitrates to nitrites, that is, by the activity of the nitrate reductase enzyme.

Diagnostic method for determining the photochemical activity of chloroplasts, which is based on measuring the photochemical activity of a suspension of chloroplasts in an average leaf sample of diagnosed plants, followed by analysis with the addition of nutrients. With an increase in the photochemical activity of the suspension with the addition of a nutrient element, compared with the control, a conclusion is made about the lack of this element, with a decrease - about an excess, and with the same activity - about the optimal content.

The proposed method allows within 40-50 minutes to establish the need of plants for 12-15 macro- and microelements and make recommendations for root and foliar top dressing. The method was introduced in 80 greenhouse farms (Figure-1).

Figure-1

The granulometric composition, the content of organic matter in the soil, the gross content of nutrients, and the absorption capacity change slowly and serve as a characteristic of a specific soil difference.

The content of mobile forms of nutrients, the reaction of the soil, the composition of absorbed cations, the degree of saturation with bases change faster, especially under the action of ameliorants and fertilizers. Therefore, agrochemical surveys of soils for these indicators are carried out at certain intervals, as a rule, 1 equal in two years, or more often, depending on the amount of fertilizers and ameliorants applied. The results of such studies are presented in the form of agrochemical maps, field passports, or cartograms, and are used to determine the optimal norms, forms, timing and methods of fertilization, as well as the need and doses of ameliorants.

Soil diagnostics is a periodic determination of relatively rapidly changing agrochemical indicators of soils. Soil diagnostics makes it possible to use fertilizers and ameliorants in the most rational way, to maximize their agrotechnical, economic efficiency and environmental safety.

The most dynamic indicator determined by soil diagnostics, which can change over several days, is the content of mineral forms of nitrogen. For this reason, this indicator is not used to compile agrochemical maps, cartograms and field passports. However, for the economical and environmentally safe use of nitrogen fertilizers, annual information on the reserves of mineral forms of nitrogen is required.

For regions of sufficient and excessive moisture, soil diagnostics of nitrogen forms is carried out before the application of nitrogen fertilizers, in zones of insufficient moisture and arid climate - before the autumn application. Depending on the depth of penetration of the root systems of crops, the water and air regimes of soils during the growing season, the content of mineral forms of nitrogen is determined in soil layers up to 100, 150, 180 cm. 0-180 cm is concentrated in the 0-60 cm layer. For certain regions, the coefficients for recalculating mineral nitrogen reserves are established for layers 0-40, 0-60 cm in layers 0-100, 0-150 cm, etc.

There are several options for correcting or calculating doses of nitrogen fertilizers based on the results of diagnostics of mineral nitrogen nutrition. In all options, the stocks of ammonia and nitrate nitrogen in a particular layer are recalculated in kg/ha, and, taking into account possible nitrogen utilization factors for specific crops, the resulting value is subtracted from the total crop demand.

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